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A quality control assessment for digital x-ray radiography through pixel values based signal and noise characteristics.

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ABSTRACT

Quality of x-ray image is a major factor for the correct clinical diagnoses in radiology. A quality control (QC) programme for medical x-ray imaging is essential to preserve quality of the images. Implementation of an effective quality assurance programme to ensure the high quality of images is a responsibility of a medical physicist in the hospital. However lack of relevant, expensive QC tools has become a challenge to maintain the quality of medical x-ray equipment in developing countries such as Sri Lanka. This article presents a simple, low cost QC procedure to measure the quality of a digital x-ray detector and image reader in occasionally through the analysis of signal and noise of digital images. The mean of the pixel value within 5 mm x 5 mm region of interest (ROI) of a uniform digital image is used to estimate signal and standard deviation (SD) of pixel value within the ROI used to estimate noise. This study suggests good baseline tests for QC through the linear relationship of pixel value based signals versus $\ln [mAs]$ and SNR versus $\ln [mAs]$. Stable signal, noise and SNR characteristics of an image will indicate stability of the quality of the imaging device. Then present experiment creates base line for signal and noise assessment for future analysis. Likewise signal to noise ratio (SNR) characteristics can be used to compare image performance between two equipment or two set up.

Keywords: Digital Radiography, Quality Assurance, Signal, Noise.

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INTRODUCTION

X-ray imaging is the most important technique in the diagnostic medicine to take two dimensional images of human body. When x-ray beam passing through the human body, depending on the electron density of tissue the photons undergo attenuation and the transmitted x-ray photons is collected at the detector as signals. Signals bring useful information of the patient anatomy described in beer's law (Guimaraes et al. 2009; Potts, 1987) and it is converted into a digital image by digital imaging system. Digital image is a matrix of pixels and pixel is the smallest controllable element of the image. Brightness of each pixel is denoted by pixel value. Pixel value represents the number of photons reached to the corresponding area of the detector (Johnston & Fauber, 2015; Vogelnest & Allan, 2015). X-ray machine has a control console to set the desired kVp (peak kilo voltage), mAs (milli amperes) or mAs (mA multiplied by the desired exposure time) for the x-ray tube and these factors influence the image quality as well as patient dose.

Brightness of pixels should be uniform in a recorded digital radiography (DR) image of a uniform object. However the fluctuations of the x ray photons reaching to the detector from point to point change the brightness randomly. This random variation in the brightness which is not related to the patient anatomy is produced in practice of the DR imaging even when the object is uniformed. This variation does not have a particular pattern and it gives a mottled, grainy, textured, or snowy appearance in the image. This random variation in image brightness is named quantum noise and it limits the detection of objects in the image (Johnston & Fauber, 2015; Gupta, 2013).

However all medical images contain some visual noise. Noise reduces the image quality; hence it is commonly used to describe the quality of images as well as equipment (Goyalet et al., 2018). Then noise is a basic measure of image quality (Alsleem & Davidson, 2012). A set of noise measurements that is taken just after the installation of a machine can be used to establish baseline data set for QC of equipment. Base line data will be compared with the future data to analyse quality changes with the usage and aging of equipment. Signal to noise ratio (SNR) is a better way to compare the noise level of images. It is a measure the ratio of true signal to noise (Easton, 2009). Low SNR indicates high noise level related to the useful signal, as well as a high SNR indicates the low noise level. Therefore high SNR indicates high image quality (Easton, 2009; Vano, 2008)

Although medical physicists in the hospitals bound to assure the quality of diagnostic imaging systems, lack of relevant, expensive QC tools has become a great challenge to establish QC culture in developing countries such as Sri Lanka. This study introduces a simple, low cost QC procedure for digital detectors and image reader through the noise analysis of digital image. It will be a great solution for high cost QC tools and a good stimulator to establish a QC culture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DRX-3724HD tube type TOSHIBA KXO-50S general x-ray machine with Care stream Direct view Classic Computer Radiography (CR) system were subjected to this study. 30cm X 30 cm, 10 cm thick water phantom was placed on the top of a CR cassette and positioned on the couch. The setup was imaged with the settings of 80 kVp, because most x-rays used in medical imaging are between 40 and 120 kVp. 25 cm X 25 cm field size at 100 cm source to detector (cassette) distance (SDD) was set up for different mAs. Mean of the pixel values and standard deviations of the pixel value in a 5 mm x 5 mm, square shape ROI in phantom image area was recorded with the corresponding mAs using the software of the (CR) system. After erasing previous image using the software, the cassette was

positioned at 100cm SDD and x-ray beam was blocked by placing a lead sheet(10 cm X 10 cm X 0.66 cm) on the cassette. 5 cm X 5 cm of shielded area was exposed with 80 kVp with different mAs. Mean pixel value of a 5mm X 5mm ROI in the centre of shielded cassette area was recorded as offset pixel value.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

X-ray beam is a shower of x-ray photons and each individual photon is called quanta. mAs controls the quantity of x-ray photons produced by the x-ray tube. mAs setting of the x-ray equipment is directly proportional to number of quanta of the x-ray beam (Carroll & Quinn,2018). X-ray quanta reach to the object or the patient as well as to the image detector in a random pattern even when object (patient) is uniformed. The random pattern of the x-ray quanta fluctuates the image pixel values from pixel to pixel. Therefore mean of the pixel values within a small ROI in a uniform image is a close representation to the signals from the x-ray beam (Strauss & Rae, 2012).

mAs set up of a machine represents the number of x-ray quanta in the x-ray beam (Langland et al., 2002; Damulira et al., 2019). Hence the relationship between signals and mAs is linear for a given technique. However the experimental relationship between mean of the pixel value of a ROI in the phantom image and mAs settings was non-linear. Limitation of vacant trap holes in between the valance and conduction bands of the PSP crystal layer in the detector decrease the signal absorption for high mAs creates weak response of the detector or the laser light intensity of the image reader may not be enough to readout all trapped electrons during the reading process at high mAs (Rowlands, 2002)is responsible for the non-linearity. Figure 1, the best fit relationship between signals (mean of the pixel values of the ROI) versus ln[mAs] was a linear with the calculated correlation coefficient (R²) value of 1.0. The relationship of signals vs mAs is only changed by the kVp, experimental set up as well as equipment failure or aging (Seibert, 2004). Therefore this test is a good baseline for QC and it will identify chronic failures of the equipment.

Figure 1: The graph of pixel value based signals versus ln [mAs] of the Direct view care stream CR system for 80 kVp at 100 cm SDD for 25 cm x 25 cm field size.

Signals come from variety of mechanical functions such as properties of cassette, image plate and electronic components, electrical and optical leakage, initial additionally to the x-ray quanta. These mechanical signals may contribute to the mean of the pixels values of the 5 mm x 5 mm ROI. They are not related to the exposure and anatomical structure of the patient and represented by offset pixel value (Scarfe & Angelopoulos, 2018). Offset pixel value is the mean of the pixel values in a 5 mm x 5 mm ROI of an image which was taken by blocking direct x-ray flux to the detector. However to compare offset pixel value with different mA settings, exposure of 80 kVp was used with a 0.66 cm lead shielding. The amount of anatomical related signal was calculated by subtracting offset pixel value from the mean of the image pixel values within the 5 mm x 5 mm ROI. A small offset value (4) was recorded by the experiment and it is suggested that the signals from the mechanical errors of the equipment is not significant. However, the offset pixel value may be changed by usage and aging of the cassette, image plate and electrical components of the system with the time. Therefore repeatability and constancy of the offset pixel value are preferable evidences for quality of a DR system. The present off set value will be the baseline test for future comparisons.

Figure 2: The graph of pixel value based noise versus mAs of the Directviewcarestream CR system for 80 kVp at 100 cm SDD for 25 cm x 25 cm field size.

Fluctuation of the image pixel values adds noise effect to the x-ray image. The noise appearance by the random pattern of the x-ray quanta is called x-ray quantum noise (Goyal, 2018). Although the structure of the film, intensifying screens, or digital receptors can introduce noise into images, the quantum noise is the most significant noise source in plain x-ray imaging applications (Penelope & Williams, 2008). The intrinsic fluctuation of the quanta or the pixel values can be determined by the standard deviation (SD) of pixel values within the ROI in the phantom image (Alsleem & Davidson, 2012). The SD of image pixel values of the small ROI in the phantom image was considered to quantifying the quantum noise from x-ray beam as in equation 1.

$$\text{Noise} = \text{SD of the photon concentration of ROI} = \text{SD of the pixel values at ROI} \text{-(1)}$$

The experiment data of noise was slightly decreased when increased mAs and taken low values with respect to the signal values as shown in figure2. These observations of noise indicate the high quality

of the imaging device. As well as signal and offset value characteristic, noise variation with mAs creates a base line experiment to analyse the quality changes of the Instrument.

However, It is not impartial for comparing image quality using either signal or noise individually, since they have opposite behaviour. However SNR represents both signal and noise simultaneously. SNR is a better factor to analyse and compare the image quality of digital x-ray images (Chan et al.,1990).SNR vs ln [mAs] was shown in figure 3 and SNR was calculated by equation 2 using both pixel value based signal and noise values. SNR characteristic is important to compare image qualities of different imaging systems with same technique. As well as the behaviour of signal and noise with the mAs settings, the SNR vs mAs can be used as a baseline curves for QC.

$$\text{SNR} = \text{Useful Signals} / \text{Quantum Noise} \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

Figure 3: the graph of SNR versus ln [mAs].

CONCLUSION

Setup value of the mAs represents the number of x-ray photons called quantity of x-ray quanta from a x-ray tube. It governs the amount of useful signals with x-ray quanta which reaches to the image detector in medical imaging. Mean of the pixel values within a small ROI in an image of uniform water phantom is a close representation to the signals from the x-ray beam and SD represents the noise. Although signals are proportionately related to the mAs, linear relationship of signals (mean of the pixel values of the ROI) versus mAs is deviated by the weak response of the detector or the image reader at high mAs. However signals (mean of the pixel values of the ROI) versus ln [mAs] is linear with the calculated correlation coefficient (R²) value of 1.0. This relationship is only changed by the equipment failure or aging for fixed 80 kVp and same experimental set up. It can be used as a baseline for QC and it will identify chronic failures of the detector and image reader. Noise is inversely related to the mAs, hence greater mAs increase the quality of the image. As well as the behaviour of signal, noise with mAs should not be changed for same set up of an instrument with time, if there is no equipment fault. The simple calculation method of SNR by using pixel values is a great measure of image performance. The relationship of SNR vs ln [mAs] is linear with the calculated correlation coefficient (R²) value of 1.0. Study of SNR introduces good baseline tests for QC as well as

signal and noise analyses. As well as the SNR analyse by using pixel values of images will be a great measure of image performance between different x-ray equipment as well as different setups.

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